

PACIFICUS

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- Spotlight on Emerging Writers
- Poetry
- Short Stories
- Essays
- Creative Corner
- Others

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RASMINDA W. DIPATUAN, MAEd

Associate Professor I

Mindanao State University

Integrated Laboratory School-Marawi City

“IF ONLY I COULD”

If only I could,
To be a falcon is my greatest want,
Soaring high where winter breezes flaunt,
To feel the kiss of nature's gentle breath,
On the stairs of the thick blue clouds, defying death,
And see the beauty of the lands beneath.

If only I could,
To be a blue whale is my deepest desire,
Swimming on the depth of the vibrant pyre,
To ride on the current where wild creatures roam,
Counting some fishes' kinds in the underwater home,
And to explore the vastness of the ocean's dome.

If only I could,
A knight for humanity is my heart's true desire
To shade and shelter the ones oppressed by fire,
From those who crave the nation's wealth and might.
Shaking the oppressor's pride and greed,
To awaken the weak to fight their rights.

If only I could,
To hear my name on the page of history is another dream of mine,
Like Alexander the Great did along ago
Bringing honor and pride to my beloved ones and country,
Fighting by the side of my brotherhood,
To lighten up their burdens are my goals so well.

If only I could...
When Malakalmaot will come to fetch me,
How I wish to die in peace, with purest body, heart and soul.
I will convey to him the meaning of Salam and Shahada with Allah's Grace.

And willing to go with him in the Jannatul Ferdauz, insha Allah.
But, because I am just only an empty creature so weak,
Offering prayers are only my way I can do for everything.

